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The KPI Editorial Board

Marcin Lawenda
Fotis Karayannis
Ad Emmen
Pieter Schipper
Michael Maragakis
Jan Wiebelitz

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e-IRGSP5
P.O. Box 93575,
NL-2509 AN The Hague,
The Netherlands
Phone: +31 (0)70 344 0526
E-mail: kpi@e-irg.eu

Visiting address

Java Building, Laan van Nieuw Oost-Indië 300
NL-2593 CE The Hague
The Netherlands

Executive Summary

In this report, we provided a summary of the work conducted in the e-IRGSP5 in the area of collection, aggregation and publication of policy and cost-related information/metrics/Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). In the first place, we have defined the audience to which it is addressed, being mainly funding agencies and policy makers in the area of e-Infrastructures, EU-funded e-Infrastructure projects and managers, along with individual users/researchers. We also outlined general rules, which lead to the definition of indicators that fulfil its role.

The internal methodology and analysis tracks' process we conducted is then presented. The analysis of the problem is very difficult and comprises many levels. It resulted in an approach composed of three tracks where different perspectives are considered: information from projects, literature review and H2020 goals and impacts. Project investigation, interviews, literature review, conference discussions show us that many projects are not prepared for discussion especially in the area of interest of this project, namely policy and financial aspects. While technical and operational indicators in many cases are decently recognized in the projects, the policy and financial metrics seem to be less relevant and analysed. Especially financial information is very hard to retrieve from projects and even more difficult for the e-Infrastructures, including their national components. However, some basic level information is required for accountability and transparency, which may also contribute to assessing the effectiveness of the funds spent and the ultimately the competitiveness of e-Infrastructures in comparison with commercial commodity services. It is noticeable that many of the measurements presented by projects as KPIs are only metrics. External experts have been involved in the project work, including a professional accountant with experience in e-Infrastructures. The external financial and policy experts, supported us in our work, and guided us with numerous suggestions.

The proposed methodology for the collection of such indicators is then presented; a three-step approach for setting and collecting indicators is proposed, which is aligning the defined metrics with impacts and goals determined by funding institutions, in-line with the e-IRG KPI framework document¹. The first step is the specification of high-level goals of the involved actors (including mainly the e-Infrastructures themselves, the funding agencies and the end users), second, the classification of goals into broad categories and third, the harmonisation of indicators and a basic categorisation of KPIs.

Next we provide a proposed list of metrics divided into three categories: H2020 generic, applicable for most of the EU funded projects and e-Infrastructures, eInfra generic – more specialized on e-Infrastructures but still general, and eInfra specific – serving as examples more-oriented on specific eInfra projects' activities. Financial metrics are also provided in a similar approach, which allow economic-oriented monitoring.

We are concluding with the set of recommendations on future developments and the evolution of the European e-infrastructure landscape and associated costs.

¹ Evaluation of e-Infrastructures and the development of related Key Performance Indicators," 2017. <http://e-irg.eu/kpi>.

I. Introduction

Metrics/indicators and in particular Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) become more and more popular tools in many areas of functioning of various activities. They show their usefulness primarily in monitoring the progress of activities, which are crucial to achieve specific goals and improve the performance of endeavour process. It is good to recall in this context the difference between a metric and a KPI. A metric captures some aspect of a project, organisation or service preferably in a numerical format. So, it is something that can be measured. If a metric is used to show how well a predefined goal is achieved, the metric is a Performance Indicator. When the goal is very important, it is called a Key Performance Indicator (KPI). So, every KPI is a metric, but not every metric is a KPI.

The EC, noticing the significant importance of KPIs, increasingly implements their application in many European research projects including e-Infrastructure projects. One such example are two statements from Augusto Burgueño-Arjona, the Head of Unit of e Infrastructures and Science Cloud. He indicated the importance of “Usefulness of the (e-Infrastructure) services” used by their users and robust KPIs which are used to measure that. Moreover, he has signified that KPIs should be used to monitor implementation progress in areas like “the cost of the services”, “the use of services”, and “linking indicators to the implementation of excellence science”.

The primary goal of this deliverable is to present the work that has been performed as part of the e-IRGSP5 project in the area of retrieval, provision, aggregation and analysis of policy information with impact on the development of EC-funded e-infrastructures, including Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and cost-related information, in coordination with the funded e-Infrastructure initiatives. It covers the methodology, including a proposed classification of metrics with relevance to the e-IRGSP5 work, a proposed list of indicators, as well as the necessary tools to publish the information.

Metrics and in particular KPIs are intended to measure the effectiveness of investments in infrastructure, as well as to provide convincing arguments for sustainable support from funders. As metrics/indicators/KPIs, in particular in the policy and financial areas, are not straightforward and in several cases hard to define, the document deals broadly with policy and financial “information”, which may include indicators/KPIs. This is in-line with Description of the Action and the original e-IRGSP5 call scope included below.

“The activities should include the collection and aggregation of relevant policy information with impact on the development of EC-funded e-infrastructures, including KPIs and cost-related information, in coordination with the funded e-Infrastructure initiatives and made available in open formats for reuse. The collected information will enable the e-IRG with the support of independent expert panels to provide strategic advice on the evolution of the European e-infrastructures landscape and associated costs”.

Overall, this document was prepared to streamline and facilitate the process of information/indicators/KPI handling in EU-funded e-Infrastructure projects. Ideally, this document can contribute to a broader effort where a specification of a set of policy and cost information/indicators is agreed with EU and national funders, so that it can be then tracked in the upcoming years, and possibly also included by the EC as a funding requirement for each project in next framework programmes.

I.1. Target Audience

The main target group for this document are the funding agencies, and in particular the European Commission, who has specified the call text and this activity. Overall, we can distinguish three different groups that can be potentially interested in the content of this document:

- Funding agencies and policy makers in the area of e-Infrastructures, mainly European and national, who are interested in performance tracking and evaluation of their funded

projects. As EU e-Infrastructures cross national boundaries, evaluating EU projects and initiatives on policy and cost aspects, requires the inclusion of the national policies and cost components. For a proper performance tracking and evaluation framework thus, national funding agencies (besides EU ones) need to also agree on a common approach. Besides the EU and national stakeholders, other funding agencies beyond Europe may have an interest in this work.

- EU-funded e-Infrastructure projects, including the major e-Infrastructure providers, as an internal means of performance monitoring and evaluation. This is the second main target audience for this document. But first, the funders need to come up with a legal framework (e.g. inclusion of related metrics as a requirement for funding in a work programme or call), implementing an approach such as the one coming out of this document. Effort has been given in having several interaction cycles with such projects.
- e-Infrastructure users and researchers, oriented on indicators/KPIs and ontologies, as well as interested in understanding the projects/e-Infrastructures performance.

I.2 How to set KPIs that work

The KPIs provide information that is suitable to support decisions and assessment about the effectiveness of investments in infrastructure (whether therefore they meet the goals that they are supposed to meet) and provide convincing arguments for sustainable support from funders (whether therefore they meet some efficiency goals). Efficiency relates inputs to outputs.

Usually, proper KPIs have the following characteristics (the list is not exhaustive):

- Objectivity (they are subjectively measured)
- Measurability (their measurement is feasible under a cost-benefit prism)
- Cost-benefit (the cost of gathering and processing the information is less than the benefit obtained by knowing it)
- Relevance to the goals
- Timeliness (you measure something at a time that the information is still relevant for decision making and control)
- Accuracy (the values are correct and are auditable)
- Comparability (the KPIs are measured with the same methodology throughout time and therefore their values are comparable)
- Small number (keeping the number of KPIs small permits better management).

Not every metric is a KPI, but every KPI is a metric

In this context it is good to mention the difference between metric and KPI. A metric captures some aspect of a project, organisation or service preferably in a numerical format. So, it is something that can be measured. If a metric is used to show how well a predefined goal is achieved, the metric is a Performance Indicator. When the goal is very important, it is called a Key Performance Indicator (KPI). So, every KPI is a metric, but not every metric is a KPI.

2. Internal methodology and analysis

The project devised an internal methodology to come up with a set of harmonised policy and financial information/indicators/KPIs. The internal methodology is composed of different analysis tracks, including interaction with the e-Infrastructure community and also the engagement of the external experts.

The main philosophy of the internal methodology has been to provide some quick results via an agile approach that can be shared and discussed with the relevant stakeholders and constitute exemplary cases that can be showcased. This also addresses the recommendations made at the first e-IRGSP5 review, towards an agile approach and feedback loops with the related stakeholders.

2.1 Analysis tracks

The internal methodology consists of three main analysis tracks and overall six steps (another three steps) that are described further in the next sub-sections.

- **Track 1 - The collection of information/indicators/KPIs from a representative set of e-Infrastructure projects²** (through polling the projects, and in particular via e-mails and interviews)
- **Track 2 - The review of the state of the art, including both e-Infrastructures and the market³** (through literature review/desk research)
- **Track 3 – Analysis of H2020 goals and impacts** (through analysis of H2020 programme assumptions digging down to eInfra-related general and specific calls)

All “tracks” run in parallel and are based on the so-called “agile-approach”, i.e. instead of an in-depth approach of all projects that would have taken time to organise and extract results, go for a smaller set of projects and documents, that can quickly produce some results that can be openly shared and discussed, and gradually be improved in next cycles.

Figure 1. The project internal agile methodology

² Metrics collected from e-Infrastructure projects: <http://e-irg.eu/kpi-collection>

³ Metrics collected under the state of the art process: <http://e-irg.eu/kpi-sota>

Based on the analysis and the feedback received from all sources, namely the projects, the interviews, call texts, the external experts, this step includes a generalisation, aggregation and harmonisation process, in order to come up with the set of indicators and recommendations towards the projects and other stakeholders. The indicators are classified as policy, financial and other, while under financial KPIs, there is a list of indicators that have as a requirement preparatory actions (such as pre-agreed financial methodologies to calculate the costs) before they can be adopted. Of course, all indicators will require some preparatory actions including possible legal agreements in the work programmes, which may include the Member States in case the e-Infrastructures are to be financially evaluated, since they comprise national components.

3. Proposed methodology - Three-step approach

The first step is the specification of high-level goals of the involved actors (including mainly the e-Infrastructures themselves, the funding agencies and the end users), second, the classification of goals into broad categories and third, the harmonisation of indicators and a basic categorisation of KPIs.

The first step is about the goals of e-Infrastructures themselves, the funding agencies and the end users. It is important to remember that the KPIs defined to keep track of e-Infrastructures progress should in the first place reflect goals set ahead of venture. It needs to be stressed out why these KPIs were measured by the projects, and which is the underlying goal behind them. Despite the increasing number of metrics, some could be found in the EC elaboration⁴. As already mentioned, two groups of goals should be considered: the funding agencies and the end users. The last group (end users) is difficult to capture but that of funding agencies would be retrieved by written documents⁵ as well as declarations made by EU officials (e.g. Augusto Burgueño-Arjona Head of the Unit "eInfrastructure & Science Cloud" at European Commission's Directorate General for Communications Networks). There is also another report issued in June 2018 under the title A NEW HORIZON FOR EUROPE Impact Assessment of the 9th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation⁶.

The second step is the classification of the goals in broad categories. There should be metrics/KPIs that are generic and others that are project-specific. Both these categories should refer to policy and cost issues. Thus, the suggestion is that firstly a small number of generic policy and generic cost KPIs could be identified. These KPIs should be based on the goals identified in step 1 for funding agencies and be able to be used for assessment and comparisons (throughout time for the same project - cross-sectional for similar projects). Secondly, a number of policy and cost related KPIs that are more project-specific should be identified. These metrics should take into account the specificities of projects, should be related to the project goals identified in step 1 and benefit from what has been done so far as identified in current practices and the state-of-the-art section.

The third step is a sum up of steps 1 and 2, the harmonisation of indicators with a further categorisation of KPIs. The KPIs should be justified as proxies for the goals identified. Of course, measuring the goals is not easy, and KPIs maybe not capture the impact but they should be designed having this in mind.

⁴ "How to set KPIs that work," <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/content/how-set-kpis-work>.

⁵ "Horizon 2020 indicators - Assessing the results and impact of Horizon 2020," <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/news/horizon-2020-indicators-assessing-results-and-impact-horizon>.

⁶ "A New Horizon for Europe, Impact Assessment of the 9th EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation," <http://knowledgebase.e-irg.eu/documents/243153/246094/Impact+Assessment+of+the+9th+EU+Framework+Programme+for+Research+and+Innovation.pdf/b0d29544-b9d1-446b-96f2-8091c246094a?version=1.0>.

4. Proposed list of metrics/indicators

Metrics are used to measure quantifiable measurements important for specific activity performance. In this sense metrics support KPIs which in turn are used to describe the overall strategic goals and objectives.

Here, we make a number of suggestions for generic KPIs based on the KPIs and metrics we have collected from H2020 projects and the state-of-the-art review. When developing these KPIs we attempt to adhere to the following general principles:

1. the KPI's must be objectively quantifiable, to a reasonable degree, and interpretable without ambiguity,
2. the cost for measuring these KPI's must be within reason,
3. the KPI's must be adjustable to suit the project's specific goals, and reflect the degree of success in fulfilling those, while reflecting contribution to overarching H2020 objectives as well.

It has to be reiterated that metrics/indicators/KPIs and in particular in the policy and financial areas, are not straightforward and in several cases hard to define. Thus, metrics/indicators/KPIs are aiming at contributing to get a better understanding of the state of affairs and progress, and may not capture the whole picture of reality.

4.1 Policy Indicators

4.1.1 Horizon 2020 generic

Horizon 2020 generic Proposed metric/indicator	Definition	Description	Provenance	Collected metric/indicator	High-level goal /Target (if available)	Related H2020 strategy or objective	Comments
No of national e-Infrastructures networked (at EU level)	Number and % of national e-Infras made accessible to EU researchers through support from H2020	Estimates EU integration of e-Infras (for 28 MS and/or also AC)	Horizon 2020 indicators/ Cross-cutting issues/ERA realisation	As is	e-Infra integration/For NRENS all EU countries	Cross cutting issues/ERA Realisation	Applicable also for the e-Infra generic category and per area and sub-area where national e-Infrastructures exist (network, HPC, HTC, national data infra, etc.)
No of researchers with access to e-Infrastructures (at EU level)	Number of researchers who have physical or remote access to research e-infrastructures (Can be also Number of actual users divided by maximum possible number)	Estimates uptake of research e-Infrastructures	Horizon 2020 indicators / Excellent Science	As is	e-Infra uptake/Was 22.000 at FP7, target value for end of H2020 was 42.000 (another 20.000)	Excellent Science	Take into account aspects like nationality, country, gender of the researcher; legal status and activity type of the employing organisation
Widening participation (in e-Infras)	Number of third countries (besides MS+AC) whose e-Infras are made accessible to	Estimates participation beyond MS+AC	Horizon 2020 indicators/ Cross-cutting	Adapted to e-Infrastructures	Third countries participation-collaboration	Cross-cutting issues/Widening participation	

	EU researchers (through support from H2020 or other means)		issues/Widening participation				
No of SMEs introducing innovations via development/use of e-Infrastructure (via support from H2020)	Number of SMEs introducing innovations to the company or market via the development or use of e-Infrastructures	Assesses e-Infra impact to innovation	Horizon 2020 indicators/ Industrial leadership	Adapted to e-Infrastructures	Number of SMEs that have introduced innovations (50% for H2020 under Industrial Leadership pillar)	Cross-cutting issues/Widening participation	Covering the project period plus three years;

4.1.2 e-Infra generic

Proposed metric/indicator	Definition	Description	Provenance	Collected metric/indicator	High-level goal	Related H2020 objective or call	Comments
No of national e-Infrastructures networked per area: network-HPC- HTC-national data infra, other services (if applicable)	Number and % of national e-Infras made accessible to EU researchers through support from H2020	Estimates EU integration of e-Infras (for MS and also AC)	Adapted from Horizon 2020 indicators/ Cross-cutting issues/ERA realisation	Adapted for e-Infra layers	e-Infra integration/For NRENS all countries	Cross cutting issues/ ERA Realisation	Multiple indicators; Applicable per area and sub-area where national e-Infrastructures exist. For national computing-data centres depends on funding-access policy Other services can be AAI, middleware, software, VREs, tools, etc.
No of researchers with access to e-Infrastructures per area: network-HPC- HTC-national	Number of researchers who have physical or remote access to research e-	Estimates uptake of research e-Infrastructures	Adapted from Horizon 2020 indicators/ Excellent Science	As is	e-Infra uptake	Excellent Science	Multiple indicators; Take into account aspects like nationality, country, gender of the researcher; legal status and

data infra, other services (if applicable)	infrastructures area						activity type of the employing organisation Other services can be AAI, middleware, software, VREs, tools, etc.
No of e-Infra policy papers (at EU level)	Edition or contributions to e-Infra policy roadmaps and strategy papers at EU level	Measures policy contributions	Adapted from INDIGO-datacloud	Number of contributions to roadmaps, policy papers	Contribute to overarching policy objective	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2 : unclear / multiple	Define 'contributions', 'roadmaps', 'discussion papers'
User satisfaction in e-Infrastructures (at EU level) and per area: networking, HPC/HTC, EOSC-data, other services	An overall rating of satisfaction from the majority of the users responding to the satisfaction surveys.	Assesses user satisfaction and services usefulness; to be based on surveys repeated at specific intervals of time	Adapted from e-IRGSP5	Delegates satisfaction	Stakeholder satisfaction	H2020-INFRA-SUPP-2016-1 : Expected impact: Facilitate the exchange of experiences and good practices between the national and/or regional policies and programmes;	Multiple indicators; Qualitative; Pay attention to perform survey on representative group of users
Community engagement in e-Infrastructures (at EU level) and per area: networking, HPC/HTC, EOSC-data, other services	Number of communities-disciplines engaged in developed solutions	Assesses the community engagement	Adapted from INDIGO-Datacloud	Number of ESFRI communities that have adopted INDIGO solutions by the end of the project	Assess community engagement / services uptake	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2 : Scope (3)	Define 'communities', 'engaged', 'solutions'
% of National Open Science strategies in EU 28 and also EU+AC	Percentage of countries who has published a national Open	Assesses the progress of countries with	State of the Art	State of the Art	Assesses Open Science progress at EU level	Open Science strategy	Data (category)

	Science strategy across the EU	regards to Open Science policies					
No and % of Open Access (OA) publications (at EU level)	Estimate % of open access publications divided by total (at EU level)	Assesses the status of Open Access policy for publications	OPENAIRE Connect	European Open Access	Contribute to assessing the OA overarching policy objective	H2020-INFRA-SUPP-2016-1: Open Access to Scientific Info	Data (category) Estimation
No and % Open datasets at EU level (OpenAIRE)	Estimate % of open datasets published at EU level (OpenAIRE)	Assesses the status of Open Access policy for data	OpenAIRE Connect, EGI-Engage	OpenAIRE, EGI-Engage	Contribute to assessing the overarching OA policy objective	Open Access to Scientific Info ; EINFRA-1-2014 : Expected impact: Increased availability of scientific data for scientific communities independently of them having already embraced or not e-science; this will be measured by cross-border data traffic over the research networks in Europe as a proxy.	Data category; Attempt to estimate the % divided by total also (if possible)
Number of publications / patents via using e-Infrastructure services and tools (at EU level)	The number of publications / patents awarded to the e-Infrastructure users using related e-Infra resources	Contributes in assessing the impact of e-Infrastructures (e.g. HPC, VREs, services) via publications and patents	H2020 (adapted to e-Infra) - Assessing the results and impact of Horizon 2020	H2020 - The publications / patents awarded on the basis of research activities supported by e-Infrastructures	Assess impact of e-Infra resources to publications and patents	H2020 indicators	Peer reviewed publications; Patent applications and awards

Contribution to standards	Number of contributions to standards coming from e-Infrastructure project developments	Contributes in assessing the contribution to standards	INDIGO-Datacloud	Number of contributions to standards coming from INDIGO developments	Contribute to overarching policy objective	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2: Scope (3)	Define 'contributions', 'standards', 'developments'
Industrial engagement in e-Infrastructures including Public-Private Partnerships (at EU level)	Number of elaborated public-private partnerships and business cases commissioned by industry	Assesses industry's engagement in e-Infrastructures	INDIGO-Datacloud	Number of business cases elaborated	Industry engagement-interaction	H2020-EINFRA-2014-2: Scope (2)	Define 'business cases', 'elaborated'

4.1.3 eInfra call-specific

Metric/indicator	Definition	Description	Provenance	Collected metric/indicator	High-level goal	Related H2020 objective or call	Comments
User satisfaction on implemented services/tools (call-specific)	Number of external users that have contributed to specifications and evaluation.	Assesses user satisfaction via surveys by external users	Multiscale Genomics	Adapted (generalised); Degree of acceptance of services/tools by external users	User satisfaction; Project output adoption	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1: Expected impact: contribute to increased take-up of collaborative research and data sharing by new disciplines, research communities and institutions.	Define 'external users', 'contributed', 'specifications', 'evaluation'. Qualitative; May be poorly quantifiable.
International cooperation (call-specific)	Number of international collaborations established using provided solutions	Assesses international cooperation	PRACE-5IP	International Cooperation	Contribute to overarching policy objective	H2020-INFRA-SUPP-2016-1: Expected impact: Encourage the pooling of resources between infrastructure operators at European level in order to face the grand challenges and to	Projects awarded to "foreign projects" (i.e. projects with PIs from a different country (recorded as the primary institution of the PI) than

						foster a culture of co-operation between them, spreading good practices and encouraging infrastructures to develop in complementary ways.	<i>the machine on which the research is executed)</i>
Data interoperability (call-specific)	Number of cases where data interoperability is implemented	Assesses level of data interoperability	VI-SEEM	Provide data interoperability across disciplines	Contribute to overarching policy objective		Define 'interoperability', 'disciplines'
No of contributions to RDA outputs/recommendations by community or project	Number of contributions to RDA outputs/recommendations from a community or project	Contributes in assessing the contribution to standards/ RDA goals (data sharing and interoperability)	State-of-the-art	-	Contribute to overarching policy objective (standards) and RDA goals	Research Data Alliance	Contributions to ICT specifications may also be relevant. Adoption of these outputs also needs to be assessed, however this is more challenging and indicators more subjective (i.e. no of adoption cases)
HPC competence involvement network	Number of HPC centres exchange best practices and pool technical, expertise or business resources	Shows HPC centres engagement in networking activities	SESAME-NET	Number of HPC Centres involved in the Network	Project product adoption	EINFRA-6-2014: Scope: (1) networking of existing HPC competence centres providing HPC services to exchange best practices and pool technical, expertise or business resources;	Define 'involved'
Open specific datasets	Number of problem-specific datasets managed by the project		EVER-EST	Number of Earth Science Datasets managed by the System	Project product adoption/ contribute to overarching policy objective	H2020-EINFRA-2015-1: Expected impact: (VREs) will contribute to increased take-up of collaborative research and data sharing by new disciplines,	Define 'managed'

						research communities and institutions.	
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4.2 Financial Indicators

In general, the EC objectives through the H2020 programme are to create growth and jobs, tackle societal challenges and reinforce Europe's international competitiveness. Moreover, EU wants to pay attention to the effectiveness of public funding and EU-funded research. For e-Infrastructures, transparency and accountability are also of major importance. In addition, efficiency, effectiveness and having cost control is also importance. Finally, e-Infrastructures may sooner or later have to prove being competitive compared to commercial market commodity services. Taking into consideration the three-step approach in relation to the definition of metrics and KPIs, we propose the following financial generic metrics.

4.2.1 Horizon 2020 generic

Proposed metric/indicator	Definition	Description	Provenance	Collected metric/indicator	High-level goal/Target (if available)	Related H2020 strategy or objective	Comments
Average FTE costs (Personnel costs to FTEs) (at EU and programme levels)	Average FTE cost in Euros: Total personnel costs divided by total number of FTEs; At programme level.	Provides an indication of average cost per FTE in e-Infras. Assesses the impact of H2020 on growth and jobs through indicators at programme level, including in terms of its efficiency and quality	Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs	Adapted from H2020	Assess the average cost per researcher; this can permit estimations about future projects and also would define a range of salaries for several purposes	Growth and Jobs creation	It should not include outsources of contractors' FTEs (only FTEs paid directly by the organizations) EU-funding only;
No and % of outsourced FTEs to FTEs (average outsourced cost) (at EU and programme levels)	Average outsourced cost in Euros and also as a percentage: Total outsourced cost divided by the total number of outsourced FTEs and	Provides an indication of average outsourced cost per FTE in e-Infras and also the percentage of outsourced work. Gives	Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs	Adapted from H2020	Assess the average outsourced cost; this can permit estimations about future projects	Growth and Jobs creation	EU-funding only;

	corresponding percentage; At programme level.	an indication of the personnel cost structure					
Female personnel participation (at EU and programme levels)	Percentage of female personnel budget to the total programme personnel budget	Assesses the participation of women in e-Infras	H2020 indicators / Gender issues	Adapted from H2020	Assess the gender balance in e-Infrastructures	Gender balance	EU funding;
SME participation	Percentage of budget assigned to SMEs to the total budget	Assesses the participation of SMEs in e-Infras	H2020 indicators / SME participation	Adapted from H2020	Assess the SME participation in e-Infrastructures	SME participation	EU funding;
Participation of third countries (at EU and programme levels)	Percentage of programme budget assigned to third countries to (divided by) the total programme budget	Assesses the participation of third countries in e-Infras	H2020 indicators / Widening participation	Adapted from H2020	Assess the participation of third countries in e-Infrastructures	Widening participation	EU funding;

4.2.2 e-Infra generic

Proposed metric/indicator	Definition	Description	Provenance	Collected metric/indicator	High level goal-strategy	Related H2020 objective or call	Comments
Average FTE cost at e-Infra (or e-Infra area levels) (Personnel costs to FTEs)	Average FTE cost in Euros: Total personnel costs divided by total number of FTEs; Again, at e-Infra or area level.	Provides an indication of average cost per FTE. Assesses the impact of H2020 on growth and jobs through indicators at project and programme level, including in terms of its efficiency and quality	Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs	Adapted from H2020	Assess the average cost per researcher; this can permit estimations about future projects and also would define a range of salaries for several purposes	Growth and Jobs creation	As e-Infras include the national nodes, national costs should be included; Should include only FTEs paid directly by the organizations (not outsourced)

<p>Average outsourced cost and % of outsourced costs to total (at EU and e-Infra (or e-Infra area) levels)</p>	<p>Average outsourced cost in Euros and also as a percentage: Total outsourced cost divided by the total number of outsourced FTEs and corresponding percentage; At e-Infra or e-Infra area levels.</p>	<p>Provides an indication of average outsourced cost per FTE in e-Infras and also the percentage of outsourced work. Gives an indication of the personnel cost structure</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs</p>	<p>Adapted from H2020</p>	<p>Assess the average outsourced cost; this can permit estimations about future projects</p>	<p>Growth and Jobs creation</p>	<p>EU-funding only; Can be estimated per e-Infra area (networking, HTC, HPC, etc.)</p>
<p>e-Infra or e-Infra area cost structure: personnel cost to total cost</p>	<p>Percentage of personnel costs divided by the total cost</p>	<p>Assesses the cost structure of e-Infrastructures and the percentage of personnel costs</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs</p>	<p>Adapted from H2020</p>	<p>Assesses the cost structure and the personnel costs, contributing towards the jobs-and-growth goal; Europe must increase the efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system</p>	<p>Growth and Jobs creation; Efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system</p>	<p>As e-Infras may include national nodes, there can be two estimations, with and without the national components. For the national components to be included a common agreed methodology may be required;</p>

e-Infra or e-Infra area cost structure: OPEX/CAPEX ratio (per year)	Percentage of Operational Expenditures (personnel, energy) to Capital Expenditures (Hardware) depreciated per year.	Assesses the cost structure of e-Infrastructures and the percentages of OPEX vs. CAPEX	Horizon 2020 indicators - Creation of growth and new jobs	Adapted from H2020	Assesses the cost structure, contributing towards the jobs-and-growth goal; Increases understanding of the efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system	Growth and Jobs creation; Efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system	As e-Infras may include national nodes, there can be two estimations, with and without the national components. For the national components to be included a common agreed methodology may be required; Similar indicators can be provided for the cost (or FTEs) of specific activities to the total cost
No of open publications per 1M Euros of project value (or other monetary value) (cumulative throughout the project)	Number of open publications per a given project value (e.g. 1M Euros) throughout a given project	Assesses the status of open access/publications compared to given funding	Adapted from state-of-the-art	SoA/Adapted for EU Open Access	Contribute to assessing the OA overarching policy objective	Open Access to Scientific Info	
No of open datasets per 1M Euros of project value (or other monetary value) (cumulative throughout the project)	Number of open datasets per a given project value (e.g. 1M Euros) throughout a given project	Assesses the status of open access/datasets compared to given funding	Adapted from state-of-the-art	SoA/Adapted for EU Open Access	Contribute to assessing the OA overarching policy objective	Open Access to Scientific Info	Similar indicators for the cost for open access publications to total project cost

Average utilisation ratio of e-Infrastructure component (computing, storage, etc.)	<i>For computing, the percentage of time the computing power is utilised. For storage, the percentage of space the storage is occupied.</i>	<i>Contributes to the assessment of the effectiveness of the infrastructure</i>	<i>e-FISCAL-SoA</i>	<i>Utilisation ration</i>	<i>Increases understanding of the efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system</i>	<i>Efficiency, effectiveness, cost control and excellence of its public research system</i>	
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A list of other indicators has already been provided in deliverable D4.1, mainly through reviewing the state-of-the-art. Examples include:

- Annual e-Infrastructure CAPEX
- Annual e-Infrastructure OPEX
- Estimated average annual total cost of e-Infrastructure
- Estimated average annual cost per core hour or estimated average annual cost per TB of storage

However, such KPIs that relate to efficiency need cost accounting methodologies to be agreed beforehand, as their calculation is complex and may require accounting systems in place. The project strongly recommends that such processes should urgently be put in place for all major e-Infrastructures, and a common such methodology needs to be agreed upon by major stakeholders. National components need also to be taken into account, while EU funding may be necessary for such harmonisation process.

4.2.3 eInfra call-specific

Apart from the metrics presented above other project-specific metrics could be developed by projects themselves.

5. Recommendations and future steps

We would like to summarize a set of recommendations intended to be starting points for further discussion around metrics and consequently KPIs for e-Infrastructures.

General recommendations to the methodology of the process of indicator definition and tracking:

- Performance monitoring expends resources, and an excess of it does not necessarily contribute to effective performance management. Superfluous performance tracking can obscure the bigger picture and risk 'analysis paralysis', where over-analysis hinders decision-making. Each metric kept must serve a purpose.
- The main objectives and expected impact of a project or e-Infrastructure must be kept in mind when choosing what to monitor. Often, careful consideration of the relation between the goal and the metric can help anticipate potential adverse effects of attempting to maximize that metric.
- Keeping track of at least one broad stakeholder satisfaction metric and involving all levels of staff in designing and evaluation of the performance management system can help identify unwanted effects of performance monitoring.
- In committing to performance targets at the outset of a project, it is advisable to leave some room for flexibility, if targets introduce unwanted effects, are overambitious or too conservative.
- Mind the difference between metrics and KPIs. Sometimes metrics are sufficient to track the development process in the projects.
- Metrics and KPIs must be well coupled with goals and impacts defined by funding organizations. It may be impossible to predefine or impose a set of indicators for an area, rather they should be determined by the appropriate persons conducting the funded activities following specified rules.
- Common standard for sharing defined metrics is required. It should facilitate the process of collection, aggregation and comparison of indicators especially between activities coming from common ground.

Specific recommendations on the H2020 e-Infrastructures assessment process:

- In order to define well-crafted indicators many perspectives must be taken into account: policy-oriented e-Infrastructure compendia, related H2020 projects, and input from other funding organisations. Pay attention that such compendia may not include related services, being orthogonal to the EOSC Services Catalogue.
- For the complete KPI chain, different perspectives and views should be considered: from H2020 generic KPIs, through the individual H2020 Call Topics Expected Impact through to eInfra generic metrics to eInfra specific project KPIs. These perspectives should be seen via using standard definitions and vocabulary, and link definitions at each level.

More targeted recommendations to the different stakeholders are provided:

- e-Infrastructure providers/initiatives/projects
 - e-Infrastructure initiatives/projects offering services should be keeping some basic information on both policies and costs; information should refer not only strictly to the project itself, but also to the whole e-Infrastructure, including possible national nodes. As the latter is not trivial, a process needs to be put in place and appropriate resources would be required (see also next recommendation). This would make easier tracking the contribution towards EOSC and EuroHPC related policies and costs.
 - e-Infrastructure initiatives/projects should be keeping their information/metrics/KPIs in a systematic way and be prepared to share it/them with a central entity.

- A central entity should also keep track of current practices and developments on information/metrics/KPIs in related e-Infrastructure projects and in funders' policies
- e-Infrastructure initiatives should keep track of metrics/KPIs on stakeholder's satisfaction (including users)
- European Commission/National funders-policy makers
 - The EC, via appropriate support, should put into effect a common process/structure for KPI collection/performance tracking in RI/e-Infrastructure initiatives/projects providing services. This can be possibly linked to the development of EOSC and EuroHPC.
 - Dedicated resources may be required for developing and agreeing a methodology for financial indicators, building on previous exercises and projects, covering not only the EU integration part, but also the national constituents of e-Infrastructures. The latter may require an agreement with the national funders.
 - National funders should have similar with the above processes, which are interoperable at EU level.
- e-Infrastructure users
 - As the usefulness of services and the user satisfaction are key for the area of e-Infrastructures, the users are encouraged to participate to relevant structure surveys and contribute to the overall assessment of e-Infrastructures.

Key Performance Indicators are very useful for the assessment process once firmly established. In several cases however, e Infrastructures seems not to be ready yet for implementation of some indicators, especially from the policy and financial fields.

That is why an intensive discussion where stakeholders are involved is required. Including stakeholders allows them on the one hand to better understand the importance of progress and efficiency indicators, and on the other hand include specific requirements in the proposed methodology.

Moreover, it seems a good idea to adopt a development approach where we start in a smooth way with a set metrics, and once they are well-established and understood to evolve to performance assessment and corresponding KPIs.

Since we are living in dynamic environment, it is not possible to provide a one and final recipe for proper e-Infrastructure performance evaluation. Rather this process should be seen as a continuous and evolving discussion aimed at finding better and better ways and measures of work evaluation and achieved results.